

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B354a and B354c
 Date: 23 March 2008
 Take Off: 08:16:49Z 16:14:45Z
 Landing: 09:46:41Z 17:14:29Z
 Flight Time 1h 30 1h 00

Campaign: VIP flights

Operating Area: Cranfield to Prestwick & Return

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stephen Mobbs	NCAS
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chem	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
7	AVAPS	Stephen Devereau	FAAM
8	Observer	Roy Kershaw	Met Office
9	Observer	Alison Wilson	Met Office
10	Observer	Sandra Pearson	Met Office
11	Observer	Mike Pilling	University of Leeds
12	Observer	Stuart Penkett	UEA
13	Observer	Claire Reeves	UEA
14	Observer	Anne de Rudder	BADC

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B354b
Date: 26 March 2008
Take Off: 14:13:23Z
Landing: 15:19:39Z
Flight Time 1h 06

Campaign: BAES Engineer Experience flight

Operating Area: Prestwick

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM1	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stephen Mobbs	NCAS
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	AVAPS	Stephen Devereau	FAAM
7	Observer	Jim Duncan	BAES
8	Observer	Steve Charlesworth	BAES
9	Observer	Brian Tuson	BAES
10	Observer	Angela ??	BAES
11	Observer		BAES
12			

Flight Track:

B354 Track 26-MAR-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B354

Date: 26 March 2008

Project: VIP & BAES Flights

Location: Cranfield - Prestwick

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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081649		T/O		125	Cranfield
090059	090445	Profile 1	9.0 - 6.2 kft	286	QNH 998
090426	090937	Profile 1	6.2 - 3.4 kft		
091045	091522	Profile 1	3.4 - 1.5 kft	299	
091844	092004	Profile 1	1.1 - 0.46 kft	184	End at 50'
092019	092508	Run 1	0.52 - 0.51 kft	181	100'
092522	092625	Profile 2	0.51 - 0.82 kft	253	
092824	092926	Orbit 1	0.95 - 0.85 kft	161	500',rh, 55deg
094641		Land	0.45 kft	064	Prestwick
140209		ASP	0.50 kft	306	Open
141323		T/O	2.9 kft	125	Prestwick
142054	143409	Run 2.1	10.0 kft	270	Over Arran
142336		Video	10.0 kft	271	Start FFC & DFC
143409	143747	Profile 3	10.0 - 7.0 kft	270	Over Arran Q991
143854	144503	Profile 3	7.0 - 1.0 kft	006	
144600	144715	Orbit 2	1.0 - 0.83 kft	315	45 deg bank
144853	145025	Profile 3	1.0 - 0.54 kft	146	
145043	151306	Run 3.1	0.62 - 1.3 kft	145	100'
151939		Land	0.49 kft	082	Prestwick
161445		T/O	2.5 kft	266	Prestwick
171429		Land	0.79 kft	341	Cranfield
171843		Shutdown	0.78 kft	309	52'04.36N 0'37.50W

B354 Track 26-MAR-08

FAAM Sortie Brief

FAAM Experience Flight

**Flight no: B354A
2008**

Date: 26th March

Take Off: 0800

Aim:

To give FAAM guests the opportunity to experience a flight on the research aircraft. There will be time in flight to move around the cabin and ask questions, then experience some of the manoeuvres performed in science sorties.

Weather conditions:

Any

Locations:

Operating Area Charlie

Instruments required:

Core instruments

Details

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1340	Take off from Cranfield		
2		Transit to Operating area	40	40
3		Perform a 60 degree banked orbit	2	42
5	0845	Profile descent to 50ft above sea	12	55
6	0900	5 minute run at 100ft	5	60
7	0905	Recover to Prestwick.		
		Land Prestwick		

Crew List

1. Captain - Alan Foster (Directflight)
2. First Officer - Ian Ramsay Rae (Directflight)
3. CCM – Tracie Hill (Directflight)
4. CCM2 - Steve Devereau (FAAM)
5. Mission Scientist - Stephen Mobbs (NCAS/FAAM)
6. Flight Manager - Mo Smith (FAAM)
7. Core Chemistry - Ruth Purvis (FAAM)
8. Guest 1 - Roy Kershaw (Met Office)
9. Guest 2 - Sandra Pearson (Met Office)
10. Guest 4 - Alison Wilson (Met Office)
11. Guest 5 - Mike Pilling (Leeds)

12. Guest 6 - Stuart Penkett (UEA)
13. Guest 7 - Claire Reeves (UEA)
14. Guest 8 - Anne de Rudder (BADC)
15. Guest 9 - -Paul Childs (BAe)
16. Guest 10 – Andrew Thain (BAe)
17. Guest 11 – Robert Gordon (BAe)

FAAM Sortie Brief

FAAM Experience Flight

Flight no: B354B
2008

Date: 26th March

Take Off: 1340

Aim:

Gravity Waves

Gravity waves are the response of a stable atmospheric flow to being forced to flow over mountains. The air rises as it passes over the mountains and descends in the lee. However, it often "overshoots" in the lee and a wave train of gravity waves form, with individual air parcels oscillating about their equilibrium level as they travel down stream. These waves have typical wavelengths of a few kilometres up to tens of kilometres. They are important for several reasons. They transport momentum vertically in the atmosphere, depositing it at higher levels where the waves break down. This is the mechanism by which the drag force due to mountains is exerted on the atmosphere. The drag is considerable, enough to make significant differences in global weather forecasting models beyond a day or two. However, because the scale of the waves is generally too small to be explicitly represented in the forecasting models, a way of representing the drag artificially, without representing the waves, has to be found. Such representations, or parameterisations, require correct understanding of the occurrence and behaviour of the waves. A second consequence of gravity waves is that they are known to be associated with severe turbulence of several forms. At upper levels they cause clear air turbulence. At lower levels, especially in the lee of mountains, they cause rotors and wind shear. Very high resolution numerical prediction models promise to be able to predict these sources of turbulence in the future but require detailed observations for their validation.

Weather conditions:

Wind of approx 20 knots

Locations:

Operating Area Charlie

Instruments required:

Core instruments

Details

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1340	Takeoff from Prestwick		
2		Perform 2 x 12 minute reciprocal runs over Arran @ FL100	30	40
3		In region of Ailsa Craig perform a 60 degree banked orbit	2	42
5	0845	Profile descent to 50ft above sea	12	55
6	0900	5 minute run at 100ft	5	60
7	0905	Recover to Prestwick.		
		Land Prestwick		

Flight:

B354

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS)

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B354

Date: 25 March 2008

Instruments

1. HORACE – Update flight summary not updating the summary window. Message “error on page” displayed at bottom of window. Okay after restarting all processes at Prestwick.

Aircraft

Intercom – FM Box can't transmit – Switch moved to “Mask” instead of “Boom” during cleaning

ISDN Emails

2 attempts to connect, 1st at approx 10:00, 2nd at 14:18Z. 2nd successful, receive all messages but nothing received.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 26/3/08

Flight No: B 354

Pre-Flighter: BW

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	inboard us
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	Cal Gas 5.17bar
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	auto/manual
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input type="checkbox"/>			
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
External Checks				
30	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Avalon Checks				<u>Signed</u>
<input type="checkbox"/>		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
<input type="checkbox"/>		ICEX applied		
<input type="checkbox"/>		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more	
<input type="checkbox"/>		Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B354:

Log	Reason
Mission Scientists In Flight	A no real science was done it is inappropriate to file a Mission Scientist log.
De-brief	A no real science was done it is inappropriate to file a debrief.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	20 May 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

No video recordings were retained from this flight.